

Laboratory Access Slot Booking System

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Abstract:- The proposed project is a computerized slot booking system to access the machines in a laboratory. Specifically it provides a time slot booking privilege to the users for their machines so that no inconvenience occurs between two users of a single machine. It has a admin part, who can control the system and user access to the booking system. The main objective of the project is to create a systematic way of accessing machines in a laboratory, Such that every members of the laboratory can get the convenience to use machines. Every user will get an access to a particular machine which will be decided by the admin upon first time registration. Every user can access a particular machine but a machine can have more than one users. To avoid the time clash between two or more user of the same machine, they can book their time slot using this booking system a night before. A slot booked by a user will be blocked for others until they cancel their booking. This will Resolve the problems of time clash and harassment of machine access.

Keywords:- Software; Laboratory; Machine; Management; Time; Slot;

1.0 Introduction:-

The project “Laboratory Access Slot Booking System” is a web development based project. System requirements to build this project are given below (as per developer’s perspective), which plays a crucial role in any development-based project. Frontend tools helps to visualize the system while backend tools help in activities which are not visible to the end user.

2.0 Hardware specification:

Processor: - Intel core i3, 10th generation

Ram: - 4GB or more

Hard disk:- 1TB

3.0 Software specification: -

Operating System- Wndows 11

Front-end- HTML, CSS

Back-end:- Mysql, PhpMyadmin

Language:- PHP

Browser: - Google chrome or any

4.0 Framework description: -

In this project PHP (Stands for Hypertext Preprocessor) is used for the frontend and backend connection. It is a popular general purpose scripting language that can be used to develop dynamic and interactive websites. It is embedded with the front end language HTML (used in the project) and backend databases. It is a server side scripting language, which means that a server executes the instructions in a script. Then the server provides data on request, and organizes the information in the database. When a web server receives a script, it will process the request and send output to a web browser in an HTML format. A web server database stores the information so other users cannot access the data and the source code. With this users can perform operations like customizing a site, making dynamic changes to website content, and accessing a database.

5.0 System design:

System design is a art of defining the architecture , components, modules, interfaces, and data for a system to satisfy a specified system.

The laboratory access slot management system has main two parts:-

1) User part:-

It is the main part of this project. The new user have to register at the beginning to get the unique password and userid. The admin will then allot the machines per user and allow them to book time slots for that particular machine. Upon successful booking the user will be notified and then they can log out from the system.

2) Admin part:-

An admin can control the total system and access all the details of the users and machines. Admin can also change the time slot preferences as per conveniences. They have the privileges to control the user access.

- **Block:-** If a user is blocked by admin, they can't access the booking page for a particular time set by the admin. The blocked user will get a message just after logging in the system.
- **Suspend:-** A suspended user will never get the access to the booking page until the admin allow him to. Suspended users will get the notification after logging in the system.
- **Allow Access:-** After the registration process the new users will be in a hold condition until admin allow them . After that they will be provided with a machine username and password which is fixed and only admin can change that.

This is the basic two parts of the project.

6.0 Desgine

6.1 Input interface design:-

The input design is the process of converting the user-oriented inputs in to the computer based data and store them in a database for future references. There are main two input portions in this project

Registration:- The new users will provide their basic data in the registration page to get the machine access.

Log-in:- Existing users will provide only the userid and password, set during the registration process, in the login page to process further.

6.2 Output interface design:-

Upon a successful slot booking , the user will be redirected to a page where they will get the confirmation of their slot booking. After that they can log out from the system. The users who are blocked or suspended by the admin will get the notification of their status. Even if one with a clear status logs in but doesn't book a slot can log out from the system.

6.3 Database design: -

Database design is the process of producing a detailed data model of a database. It contains all the needed logical and physical designs and storage parameters to generate a data definition language, which can be used to create a database. The general objective of database design is to make the data access easy, inexpensive and flexible to the user. The following tables are used in this project :-

registration (sl_no, username, password, name, course, sem, roll, ph)

user (ucode, username, password, status)

machine (mno, musername, mpassword)

store (sl_no, username, ucode)

allocation (ucode, mno)

slot_booking (ucode, mno, stime, etime, date)

6.4 ER diagram: -

The entity relationship diagram (ER diagram) displays the relationships between the entity sets stored in the database. It helps to explain the logical structure of databases. The rectangle boxes define the entity set, the oval represents the attributes of that particular entity, The diamond shape determines the relationship between the entities. The following ER diagram represents the entity framework infrastructure of this project.

Fig 1: ER diagram

6.5 Data Flow diagram: -

The data flow diagram maps out the flow of information for any process or system. It uses some defined symbols to show data inputs, outputs, storage points and the routes between each destination. It is a simple graphical formalism that can be used to represent a system in terms of input data to the system, various processing carried out on this data, and the output data is generated by this system. It is one of the most important modeling tools, that is used to model the system requirements and components. DFD shows how the information moves through the system and how it is modified by a series of transformation. It depicts information flow and the transformations that are applied as data moves from input to output. It is also known as bubble diagram. The circle defines the function, pipeline defines the database, rectangle box represents input/output of the system and the arrow indicates the data flows. The following Diagram shows the overview of the project

References: -

To develop the project systematically and in a proper way ,we took some ideas from the followings:-

- 1) Database System Concepts-- Abraham Silberschatz, Henry F. Korth, S. Sudarshan
- 2) HTML and CSS book—Kailash Chandra Upadhyay
- 3) PHP , HTML, CSS <https://www.w3schools.com/>
- 4) SQL, PHP <https://www.javatpoint.com/>
- 5) XAMPP <https://www.freecodecamp.org/>